

Research Design of the Estonian Longitudinal Study of Youth (ELSY)

Young people are the most valuable asset of Estonian society, as they represent its hope for the future in economic, cultural and societal terms. However, long-term processes such as economic globalization and international political destabilization, as well as momentous events with a global reach, such as COVID-19 and the war in Ukraine, have made the future of this young generation increasingly uncertain. The Estonian Longitudinal Study of Youth (ELSY) is developed to help us understand how Estonian young people make their transition to adulthood, which challenges they face and what factors increase their resilience in the face of uncertainty.

Estonia has undergone significant societal and economic changes since the twentieth century. Like many countries, it has seen a rising level of uncertainty due to recent crises. Under these circumstances, the transition to adulthood has become particularly challenging. Recent statistics reveal that in 2022, 10% (Statistics Estonia, 2022a) of young people (aged between 18 to 26), who are not continuing their studies, have only basic education or an educational level below that. Additionally, the dropout rate is high, approximately 20%, among those who entered secondary schools. The transition from school to labour market (LM) is also problematic. The unemployment rate among young people aged 15-26 (14.2% in 2022) is notably high (Statistics Estonia, 2022b), and so is the share of neither in education, employment, or training (NEET youth), reaching 10.5% (Statistics Estonia, 2022c) within the same age group. Therefore, we need a better understanding of the opportunities and challenges that young people in Estonia face, the patterns of trajectories that they take, and how they navigate different pathways during times of uncertainty.

Multidisciplinary longitudinal study of youth

To address these concerns and gain insight into how young people in Estonia transition into adulthood amidst uncertainty, a crucial first step is to have **high-quality data**. Such data should allow not only a wide coverage of the diversity in the transition to adulthood, but also an in-depth exploration of the experiences of young people themselves to understand how diversity comes about and how young people themselves interpret their pathways.

ELSY is planned as a multidisciplinary longitudinal mixed-methods study that aims to provide unique and representative data on the youth population in Estonia.

ELSY is going to answer questions of great societal and scientific relevance, such as:

- How do the post-compulsory educational and LM trajectories of Estonian young adults unfold in the context of increased level of uncertainty due to multiple crises? How do young people interpret the meaning of respective experiences in their transition to adulthood?

- How are micro, meso and macro level factors related to diversified educational and LM trajectories especially disrupted ones? How do young people interpret their trajectories in the light of these intersecting factors?
- How are these diversified educational, LM trajectories and social relationship domains interacting? How do young people perceive the meaning of this interplay in the context of increasingly non-linear transitions?
- How are different trajectories related to young people's aspirations and resources? How are young people's differentiated ways of making sense of their biographical experiences shaping their views of their future?
- How do young people assess their well-being? How are different trajectories and well-being mutually related and how do young people perceive (the meaning of) this relationship?

In summary, the ELSY seeks to answer questions about how young people integrate into the world of education and work and how this affects other important issues in their lives, like relationships and well-being. This will provide us with a holistic view of what it implies to become an adult in current Estonian society and allow us to understand how diversity in these trajectories is linked to (a) young people's aspirations and resources (micro-environment), (b) their position within the multiple interactive contexts of family, school and workplace (meso-environment) and (c) institutions, policies, social norms and societal events (macro-environment). Finally, our approach allows us to study the consequences of these experiences, aspirations and pathways for their future life course.

Longitudinal mixed-methods design

To answer these research questions, ELSY is designed as a longitudinal mixed-method study with three key features.

First, ELSY uses a **mixed-methods design** to understand both how the transition to adulthood unfolds and how it is experienced and interpreted by young adults. A mixed-methods design combines the generation and analysis of large-scale patterns and in-depth processes and understandings, to allow for richer insights into the diversity of the transition into adulthood. The quantitative element allows for a wide exploration of the patterns regarding the transition into adulthood, while the qualitative element provides an in-depth understanding of how these patterns come about and how young people interpret them.

Second, ELSY **will link data from survey waves to several registry sources**, which allows for full coverage of the educational and employment trajectories of the whole youth population born in 1996-2006.

Third, ELSY is a **longitudinal study** that aims at following a **key cohort born in 2006** over 10 years, starting at around age 18 until they reach the ages of 29-30 through various sub-studies to understand the transition to adulthood from a life-course perspective.

The combined longitudinal dataset

The longitudinal dataset will be constructed by linking the survey data collected during this study with administrative data from various registers. Additionally, it will be enriched with retrospective and forward-looking insights obtained from focus group interviews, biographical interviews, and ad hoc qualitative studies involving young individuals from the key cohort. For a subset of the sample, this combined dataset will be further augmented with competency scores and background school and family information retrieved from the OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) databases.

Thus, ELSY will combine data from the following sources:

- **focus group** interviews with youth from the key cohort mapping their interests and relevant subjects related to their post-compulsory education transitions, but also their readiness and preferences for participating in such a longitudinal study.
- data from different Estonian **registry databases** (e.g. Estonian Education Information System, Employment Register, Population Register etc) cover the educational trajectories, occupational and labour market transitions as well as family formation and living environment.
- **Web-based survey** (max 20 min long) collecting data (every third year) on respondents' current education and work experiences, aspirations and plans for the future, attitudes, values, well-being and mental health (will be linked to the administrative datasets).
- **biographical in-depth interviews** among young people will be used to learn how they view their lives and transitions to adulthood in the societal context of instability and insecurity.
- specific **qualitative ad-hoc case studies** will be initiated based on the results of the analysis of quantitative and administrative data.
- statistical and institutional **contextual data synthesis** is planned to support understanding the role of macro- and meso-level context.
- **PISA data** from 2022 provides elaborate measurements of **cognitive skills** which are at the respondents' command at the end of their compulsory schooling (9th grade) (for N6000, i.e., almost half of the respective birth cohort), along with detailed student background characteristics, the PISA.

The research objectives and conceptual framework will be further developed across all substudies that use different data and methods. Within this joint conceptual framing, the study is planned with a sequential logic where each successive study will use the results of the previous studies as contributions. The research instruments, datasets and findings of substudies will be linked and compared with each other to develop more complex and multi-level interpretations across the research.

Figure 1. The conceptual model of ELSY

Figure 2. Timeline of data collections and operations within ELSY

Table 1. An overview of the key concepts and clusters of variables in ELSY and the data sources from which they are derived

Key concepts and clusters of variables in ELSY				
<i>Concept</i>	<i>Cluster of variables</i>	Registers	Web survey	PISA survey
Education trajectories				
	Educational pathways and transitions	✓		
	Reasons discontinuing education and training		✓	
	Participation in non-formal education		✓	
	Participation in informal learning		✓	
Employment trajectories				
	Employment pathways and transitions	✓		
	Occupational pathways and transitions	✓		
	Information about employment (type of employment, contract, employer, job title etc.)	✓		
	Salary	✓		
	Intention to change job		✓	
	Reasons for changes in employment/occupation		✓	
Social relationships				
	Leaving parental home		✓	
	Partnership history and current status	✓	✓	
	Household	✓	✓	
	Children	✓		
	Union formation intention		✓	
	Fertility intention		✓	
Aspirations, values and attitudes				
	Education/training		✓	✓
	Work		✓	
	Combining work and personal life		✓	
	Values and attitudes towards the future		✓	
			✓	
Uncertainties, crises, and concerns for the future				
	Crises and uncertainties		✓	
	Global and national security		✓	
Resources				
	Social capital (own)		✓	
	Cultural capital (own)		✓	
	Financial situation		✓	

	Cognitive skills		✓
	Grades/exam results	✓	
Well-being			
	Health and well-being		✓ ✓
	Social integration ¹		✓ ✓
	Living conditions		✓
	Life satisfaction		✓
Background			
	Gender	✓	
	Age	✓	
	Ethnicity and mother tongue	✓	
	Migration	✓	✓
Meso-level environment			
School characteristics			✓
	Language of instruction		
	Type of educational institution		✓
	School location		✓
	Number of students		✓
Parental family			
	Parental Family climate		✓
	Socio-economic origin	✓	✓
	Economic capital (family of origin)	✓	✓
	Cultural capital (family of origin)		✓
	The index of economic, cultural and social status (ESCS) ²		✓
	Parents' involvement ³		✓

¹ Student's social integration test in PISA survey includes six questions: "I feel like I belong at school", "I make friends easily at school", "Other students seem to like me", "I feel like an outsider (or left out of things) at school", "I feel awkward and out of place in my school" and "I feel lonely at school". In addition, information on experience with school bullying is available in PISA.

² ESCS is a measure of students' access to family resources (financial capital, social capital, cultural capital and human capital) which determine the social position of the student's family/household.

The measure of socio-economic status in PISA: a review and some suggested improvements. Available from:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341978879_The_measure_of_socio-economic_status_in_PISA_a_review_and_some_suggested_improvements [accessed Nov 15 2023].

³ Parents' involvement in PISA is measured through three questions: "My parents encourage me to be confident", "My parents support me when I am facing difficulties at school", "My parents support my educational efforts and achievements".

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The ELSY research design is a collective effort. The key writing team for this short description based on the final version of the ELSY Blueprint consisted of Gerli Nimmerfeldt, Aat Liefbroer, Ellu Saar, Siyang Kong, Liisa Martma. Rosalind Edwards contributed texts for the Blueprint on mixed-methods design aspects. Jelena Helemäe, Triin Roosalu, Liis Ojamäe and Maaris Raudsepp from the Institute of International Social Studies at Tallinn University contributed to a precursor proposal from which portions were used as a starting draft of parts of the ELSY Blueprint which this short description sums up. All other YouthLife project team members (Gwendolin Blossfeld, Hans-Peter Blossfeld, Ann Berrington, Susie Weller) provided valuable comments on a draft of the ELSY Blueprint.